

First Reviser for *Rhopalum succineicollarum* Tsuneki, 1952

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Rhopalum succineicollarum Tsuneki, 1952 was made available according to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN 1999; henceforth “the Code”) in a publication that included the spellings *succineicollarum* (pg. 115, 116, 120), *succineicolle* or *suecineicolle* (pg. 116), and *succinei collearum* [sic] (pg. 117). A synonymy and citation record is provided in Leclercq (2010). Tsuneki consistently used *succineicollare* in subsequent publications, but this form is not a valid mandatory emendation of *collarum*, *collearum*, or *colle* according to the rules of Latin grammar. Tsuneki cannot be considered his own First Reviser according to Article 24.2.4 of the Code.

Haneda (2008) may have served as a First Reviser, as according to Leclercq (2010) the form *succineicollarum* was used in this work. However, this work is not accessible online, and I could not verify whether Haneda (2008) cited all forms of the original name in Tsuneki (1952). Hashimoto and Nakanishi (1999) also use *succineicollarum*, but do not act as First Revisers.

Acting as First Reviser, I select *Rhopalum succineicollarum* Tsuneki, 1952 as the available name. *Rhopalum succineicolle*, *Rhopalum suecineicolle*, *Rhopalum succineicollearum*, and *Rhopalum succineicollare* are all incorrect spellings and therefore unavailable according to Art. 24.2.3. If they are considered subsequent spellings, both Haneda (2008) and Hashimoto and Nakanishi (1999) preclude the possibility of *Rhopalum succineicollare* being a correct original spelling according to Art. 33.3.1. If they are to be considered incorrect original spellings, they have no separate availability and cannot enter into homonymy or be used as a substitute name according to Art. 32.4.

If Haneda (2008) proves to have been a First Reviser, this revision is to be considered nullified according to Art. 24.2.5 and an update will be published accordingly upon notice.

References

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